

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS IMPACT ON NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL SECURITY

Iftime I.

*Cpt., PhD candidate at "Carol I" National Defence University
Bucharest, Romania*

Abstract

The rapid rise of artificial intelligence (AI) is unfolding on a global scale, with all sectors of security becoming involved to varying degrees. At the same time, the special attention given to this emerging and disruptive technology by major powers, as well as by other states, calls first and foremost, for an analysis of its impact on both national and international security.

Therefore, this article aims to identify and highlight the development context, the objectives pursued by certain international actors, and its effects on various domains (social, political, military, and cyber). In this regard, the following research questions are formulated:

Why is AI technology important for national and international security? What are the advantages of using AI? What vulnerabilities, threats, and risks arise throughout the AI life cycle? What is the vision of certain actors on the international stage regarding the use of artificial intelligence?

Keywords: artificial intelligence, national and international security, information, advantages, threats, political, social, military and cyber.

Introduction:

Nowadays, artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly influencing both national and international security. Countries around the world are engaged in a new arms race, an *"algorithmic arms race"* [1], as shown by the AI development and implementation strategies adopted by each state and by international organizations, as well as the abundance of specialized literature on the topic. AI is part of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, aiming to make human activity more efficient through autonomous systems developed in various directions, such as: optical character recognition, machine learning, natural language processing, deep learning, adaptive neural networks, reasoning and knowledge representation, predictive networks based on intent modeling, and more.

The wide range of areas where this technology is being applied highlights a new phenomenon. The state itself is transforming by adopting this new technological trend. As one definition puts it: *"In the context of AI, state-building can be seen as the process through which the state shapes its policies, legislation, and institutions to address the challenges and opportunities related to AI [...] and understanding and analyzing the interaction between the state, civil society, and artificial intelligence becomes crucial for ensuring the effective security and resilience of national systems"* [3]. Many of the state's components, such as public administration, healthcare, education, the economy, the military system, etc. can significantly improve their performance by integrating AI into their processes.

AI is of great interest in both national and international security because it can enhance mechanisms such as: automating certain administrative processes, improving cybersecurity through autonomous systems that detect and respond to incidents, countering psychological warfare tactics, increasing the efficiency of border security, improving decision-making by collecting and analyzing data more quickly, objectively, and from

more sources, protecting critical infrastructure, and more. The role of AI in the functioning of a modern state is increasingly felt, especially due to the rapid growth in the volume of data being used. Much of this data is unstructured, scattered across various environments, and mixed with inaccurate information. Identifying and connecting this data into useful insights is becoming harder and harder for human operators.

At present, AI is one of the most important emerging and disruptive technologies. For this reason, the world's most influential leaders have made it a top priority for research, development, and funding. Its potential and impact on society are enormous. As Russian President Vladimir Putin once stated: *"whoever becomes the leader in AI will rule the world"* [11, p.8]. One of the world's major powers, China, has launched the largest effort in this field and, according to its strategy, aims to become the global leader in AI by 2030.

Artificial Intelligence and Information Management in the Socio-Political Environment

The tertiary information era we are currently in (the primary information era being the one before the internet, with newspapers, radio, television, and the secondary era being that of the internet and satellite television) is characterized by a large flow and volume of information that circulates without prior verification, and often, countering it through official statements happens too late. Therefore, an appropriate response model could be described in four steps: *"action (a real-time response; locating and tracking users who spread content against national interest); planning (developing a strategic national action plan focused on identifying and eliminating attackers' strong points); strategy (part of the national strategy must remain confidential to effectively apply action plans); use of AI tools (needed in complex activities such as locating, monitoring, correlating information, and supporting decision-making)"* [7].

Because information has a major and direct influence on national security, special attention is given to the high potential of AI to distinguish between acts of disinformation, manipulation (meant to destabilize even national security at times), and floods of redundant/ partial/ spam/ foreign interference data and real ones. Another aspect that draws increased attention to the current flow of information refers to certain attributes: “*the degree of lethality, the speed with which it can spread, and the impact that people’s belief in such information can have*”[7]. Just as the number of cyberattacks grows every day, the virtual space is increasingly flooded with false/ inaccurate information, which only generates misunderstanding and inaction. In this sense, an AI system can provide surveillance of the online environment, control over information exchange, and reporting of harmful content and actions, in the context where information is the “*weapon*” of the 21st century.

AI’s implications in information management must be very well regulated so that citizens’ rights and freedoms are respected. A counter-example is China’s AI policy. In these states, there is *de jure* a legal framework that protects citizens’ rights and freedoms, such as the “*Personal Information Protection Law (PIPL): art. 44: the right to be informed, to decide, to restrict or refuse processing; art. 45: the right to access, update, and transfer personal data; arts. 46–48: the right to request that operators explain processing rules, correct/complete/delete certain data; or in the Civil Code: art. 1032: respect for private life*” [8, p.158] etc., but *de facto*, political interest prevails, and individuals are generally under extensive surveillance, having a certain social score assigned. The government, using AI, monitors “*behavior, social interactions, affiliations, personal opinions of each person, and if these go against the policy of the Communist Party, one may even be preventively sent to re-education centers*”[5]. The declared purpose of this system is to ensure a high level of security for citizens by combating crime and offenses more effectively, but the hidden purpose is to secure the political class and regime through total population control and the limitation of some rights and freedoms. In this sense, citizens have developed a trend of wearing protective masks against polluted air or using sunglasses, aiming to fool facial recognition systems.

This technological momentum happening globally and strongly supported through many means has attracted the attention of international governmental and non-governmental organizations, as well as some major companies in the field, to the possible negative effects. The focus in expert discussions is on components such as: legality, ethics, controllability, privacy protection, reliability, fairness, transparency, etc. Although the benefits of using AI in national security are unquestionable, some defensive capabilities can be diverted for offensive purposes. In this sense, special attention may be given to social media platforms since, by their design, they are places where millions of users can communicate and share information at the same time, and they also reflect complete sets of relationships and connections between them. On these platforms, over time, terrorists have been recruited, criminal networks have

formed, attacks have been planned, crowds have mobilized for revolts and actions, and personal data theft has been and remains common. For now, AI development in social media networks is on an upward trend. Various AI-based applications and features appear regularly and are increasingly appreciated and used by a growing public.

A widely used method on social media platforms is the use of deep-fakes based on generative AI (a growing threat to state stability). These can target important activities organized at the state level (for example during elections) and can even compromise democracy, incite hatred, violence, terrorism, etc., by undermining public trust. Thus, there has been increasing focus on the responsible development of AI, an aspect shaped through various laws, conventions, regulations, national and international standards. The main issue remains that not all actors “*play*” by the same rules, and although ethical and legal norms can be introduced into AI’s reasoning algorithms, it is known that some actors have no interest in doing so.

At present, this technology is best regulated at the level of the European Union (EU AI Act; EU Framework Convention on AI, Human Rights, Democracy and the Rule of Law; GDPR regulations, etc.), NATO, and then in the United States of America, while at the opposite end are countries like China and Russia. Experts in the field have raised a warning, claiming that in this way, authoritarian regimes, which face no restrictions in developing and using artificial intelligence, could gain a considerable advantage in this race. However, this gap does not exist in reality, because EU and NATO legislation excludes the field of national and international security from the set of restrictions and development limitations imposed on AI.

The introduction of AI in the field of national security can also be explained by a current trend, based on an increasingly present nationalist and populist background at the international level, which causes any problem to be placed under the imperative of national security, due to its novelty. Artificial intelligence is often viewed in terms of its destructive potential, with the emergence of possible new threats based on the diversification of the environments in which it operates, the means used, and their complexity. As with other new technologies, these “*multiply the number of ways in which rivals and revisionists can threaten national security*”[2]. Thus, artificial intelligence has become a critical technology, and China’s rapid rise in the field, along with its desire to hold a monopoly, can be seen as a security issue.

The use of artificial intelligence for offensive purposes has enormous potential to affect all sectors of security and is undoubtedly classified as an existential threat in the medium and long term. The very fact that certain proactive and even defensive measures are already being adopted classifies AI as a potentially major threat when used with malicious intent.

Implications of AI on the Cyber and Military Environment

Artificial intelligence has a significant influence on the cyber domain, which has become an increasingly popular battlefield. It can be used both to protect computer networks and to develop more complex new

cyber threats. Increasing digitalization brings with it an equal potential for attacks. One of the most common methods to disrupt an AI-based digital system is to “poison” the algorithms used by introducing erroneous data that ultimately leads to incorrect decision-making. Once detected, state interventions must be firm and swift. Although not an example promoting democratic values, China adopted such a policy in 2023. It initially banned *Chat-GPT* because it was considered a threat to the regime, then allowed it to operate again but with restrictions, permitting only social content that “*reflects the fundamental values of socialism, must not contain subversion of state power, overthrow the socialist system, incite national division, undermine national unity, promote terrorism, extremism, ethnic hatred, ethnic discrimination, violence, obscenity, pornography, false information, or disturb economic and social order*”[4]. Thus, a new challenge arising from the use of AI by various regimes is the “*democratization of artificial intelligence*”[9].

Obtaining sensitive data and information increasingly requires less physical presence in a specific place and time. Nowadays, borders are increasingly diluted both spatially and temporally, and achieving certain objectives can be just “*one click away*”, as digitalization has imposed the transfer of data and information from physical to digital formats. In the cyber environment, actors can enjoy anonymity, and AI based cyberattacks are becoming harder to identify. There is growing emphasis on economic, political, and social destabilization actions because they have much greater and longer lasting effects than actual military actions, which also require more resources. Therefore, AI developments are needed for preventive and defensive purposes to identify and limit or eliminate these new types of attacks. The ability to discover, detect patterns, and identify intrusions or manipulations in the system exists because the system is designed that way (complex computation, self-learning, adjustment based on environmental changes, hypothesis testing, providing conclusions, decision-making, and acting within user limits), but it remains each actor’s responsibility to improve and update it with new information from the field or changes on the international scene to better adapt to new threats.

Threats generated by AI technology will be increasingly difficult to identify and counter due to its attributes such as “*technical complexity, rapid development of technologies, challenges in supply chains and life cycles, application across diverse fields, human decision-making, regulatory challenges*”[10]. Thus, the human resources involved must be increasingly specialized (due to the presence of increasingly sophisticated algorithm sets) and better educated (eliminating prejudices, unethical and unprofessional behaviors), every step in the supply chain must be secured to eliminate initial vulnerabilities, the legal framework must be constantly updated in relation to new trends, and the unified framework regulating all AI activity must be comprehensive, standardized, and detailed to cover all applications in various fields. So far, some of the most common AI threats are: “*data manipulation, data poisoning, model inversion and theft, sensitive information prediction, supply chain attacks, prompt injection, hallucinations (non-existent or unreal results), black-box*

problem (hard-to-interpret models), inadequate explanation, value trade-offs (choosing a more complex system or not), misinterpretation of AI results, evasion attacks, model drift, overfitting and under-fitting, data quality issues, misuse, over-trust, lack of human oversight, automation risks, lack of clarity, created vulnerabilities, re-identification and de-anonymization, bias”[10].

Methods used by malicious actors can affect both government digital systems and private ones, taking various forms: replicating official websites for phishing attacks, generating fake profiles and creating a manipulation mass by accessing open-source information from social networks, “*training*” AI software such as *Chat-GPT* with sensitive information that later becomes available to third parties, voice cloning and subsequent blackmail, etc. Thus, through the influence of actors aided by AI, damage can range from minor (financial fraud against an individual) to major (against a state, when the action is orchestrated at a high level and can even influence that nation’s politics). Russia remains one of the most important actors when it comes to influencing a nation’s politics. Historical examples are numerous, with their operations carried out both in Europe and across the ocean in the USA. These actions are the most dangerous because they are characterized by several attributes such as: the presence of a state-level actor, huge sponsorship, complexity of planning and execution (analyzing social grievances and desires, using certain symbols and invoking important historical personalities that stir strong feelings among the population, timing, etc.) and major negative effects. All of these are now easier to accomplish due to accelerated technologization and investments made in artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence is also useful in securing the Internet of Things (IoT), a growing field due to the widespread adoption of mass technologies. Nowadays, there is increasing focus on smart development, where every space (office, home, industrial sectors, transport, etc.) is becoming more crowded with devices and applications interconnected through the internet. However, the infrastructure and encryption methods used in this field are limited in data processing and transfer. Most of the time, lightweight infrastructure is preferred over those containing robust security protocols that consume more power and require more resources, due to the specifics of each targeted commercial sector. This, however, comes with a series of security vulnerabilities. The efficiency of IoT lies in finding the balance between security and energy consumption. One solution in this regard can be the use of AI through “*various Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) approaches that can accelerate the performance of security mechanisms for IoT networks*”[12]. These can be developed predictively to detect and forecast attacks on IoT networks at each layer (perception, network, transport, processing, application).

The military dimension is also strongly marked by AI in many ways, the main effect being as a force multiplier. Thus, we can speak of the optimization of the information cycle at each stage, shortening the duration of the decision-making cycle, supporting the fighter with intelligent weapons and more timely information,

autonomous weapon systems, adversary behavioral analysis systems, anticipative and predictive systems regarding the adversary's new movements, etc. Besides these, future armed conflicts will be about who holds information supremacy, who controls and disseminates relevant information first; *"AI networks serve as the grid and plan of the new battlefield of the 21st century"*[6]. This can only be achieved by adding a complex sensor network, distributed across all operational environments, and having AI process data rapidly and efficiently. Agility and adaptability in the military field rely both on shortening reaction times and on strategic surprise based on informational advantage. Furthermore, AI has proven to be an excellent data collection and analysis system, but the most important questions remain: Is the analysis reliable? What is the source, and has the data been altered? Were all variables considered? What were the real objectives of collecting that information? Who and how uses it? Therefore, it is necessary that the decision-maker be a real person who validates options/ recommendations resulting from the analysis through certain verification/ comparison/ control mechanisms.

At the same time, *"the United States, NATO, and its partners have identified artificial intelligence technologies as essential for ensuring technological superiority and achieving strategic military advantage"*[6], and the time to reach this goal shortens with each new innovation discovered in the field. When discussing the security of Alliance members or even global security, it is understandable that this can only be achieved through cooperation, so that AI which will cover more and more domains operates with truthful data and information under the same set of rules. However, there will always be a fine line between sharing certain information managed at the national level but necessary for an AI technology functioning at the allied level, and protecting national interests and sovereignty. Lack of consensus and trust can ultimately generate inefficient capability. This aspect is reinforced by the different views some NATO members have regarding various conflicts (for example: Hungary's position on the war in Ukraine or Turkey's stance on the war between Israel and Hamas). Another closely related problem is the interoperability of these systems. It is known that this process within NATO unfolded over a long time horizon until certain procedures, tactics, weapon systems and ammunition used, techniques, etc., were aligned. The same will apply to a potential defensive AI system operating at the allied level.

Moreover, *"becoming a leader in artificial intelligence is the key to achieving global dominance. Nations will use AI technological superiority to shape the geopolitical, social, and economic environment to their strategic advantage"*[6]. Therefore, AI technological advances will have a much faster impact on actors, shaping everything from individuals' social life aspects to the values and interests of the state. In this regard, another future goal in AI development emerges: achieving a high level of Global Situational Awareness (GSA). This early awareness of events on the international stage (those that will take place or are ongoing) will be based on adequate prior monitoring and analysis.

CONCLUSIONS:

In the context of the accelerated evolution of AI, national security remains a constant and high-priority component for every actor. At the same time, the current development of artificial intelligence is closely linked to the field of national and international security due to the high level of involvement from major international players—reflected in their adopted strategies, financial resources committed, and the advanced level at which they operate. Its importance is also emphasized by the fact that limitations and restrictions on the expansion and use of this technology are often lifted when national and international security are at stake. This is due to the efforts of both international organizations and individual states to avoid falling behind technologically compared to authoritarian actors who face no such restrictions. In this way, the emergence of new AI-based threats that would otherwise be unmanageable is prevented.

Security vulnerabilities, threats, and risks related to artificial intelligence can arise throughout the entire AI lifecycle: initiation, design, development, verification, validation, implementation, operation, monitoring, reevaluation, and decommissioning. Therefore, one of the critical requirements is that the human personnel involved must become increasingly specialized and constantly trained to detect and effectively manage any intrusion or weakness in the system. This necessity also stems from the increasing technological complexity and the rapid spread of AI across all security sectors.

With regard to other areas of application, AI must be and remain an extension of the human decision-making process, enhancing it rather than fully replacing it. A limit frequently emphasized in the literature is the prohibition of AI's discretionary actions, particularly in scenarios where decisions may affect the integrity of individuals. Furthermore, the surveillance and information-gathering activities conducted by AI in the social environment must be continuously regulated in line with technological advancements, to avoid infringing on citizens' rights and freedoms. The concept of responsible development must consistently refer to this social dimension, as it has until now.

Artificial intelligence thus represents a revolution in itself in the field of information generation and management. However, it is not enough for AI to reduce decision-making time; it must also reduce uncertainty through rigorous selection of the information used in analyses. The cyber and military domains are particularly benefiting from this technology, especially in the development of preventive and predictive capabilities. Still, due to their critical role in the state's security architecture, the information used must not only be timely and relevant but also accurate. This can be ensured by closely monitoring the data input into the system to validate its quality based on source and content.

References

1. Christopher, M.; Burton, J.; Christou, G., *The US Intelligence Community, Global Security and AI: From secret intelligence to smart spying*, 2023, URL: <https://academic.oup.com/jogss/article/8/2/ogad005/7128314?login=false>.

2. Drezner, D., How everything became national security and national security became everything, published in *Foreign Affairs*, vol. 103, New York, 2024, URL: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/3101277705/fulltext/C5CF9145AB714A98PQ/23?accountid=88069&source-type=Magazines>.
3. Gumenyuk, V.; Nikitin A.; Bondar, O; Zhydovtsec, I; Yermakova, H, The role and significance of state-building as ensuring national security in the context of artificial intelligence development, published in Wiley, 2025, URL: <https://0k11h6u52-yhttps-onlinelibrary-wiley-com.z.e-nformation.ro/doi/10.1002/aaai.12207>.
4. Kexin, Z., ChatGPT – Thype Chatbots in China: Allowed only if they provide “socialist” content, URL: <https://bitterwinter.org/chatgpt-type-chatbots-in-china/>.
5. Malaterre, A., Digital surveillance is omnipresent in China. Here’s how citizens are coping, URL: <https://theconversation.com/digital-surveillance-is-omnipresent-in-china-heres-how-citizens-are-coping-225628>.
6. Masakowski, Y., Artificial Intelligence and the future global security environment, published in *Artificial Intelligence and Global Security*, 2020, URL: <https://0k10y5vdi-y-https-www-emerald-com.z.e-nformation.ro/insight/content/doi/10.1108/978-1-78973-811-720201001/full/html>.
7. Nasser AL-Suqri, M., Gillani, M., A comparative analysis of information and artificial intelligence toward national security, published in *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, 2022, URL: <https://0k1136afs-y-https-ieeeexplore-ieee-org.z.e-nformation.ro/document/9797706/figures#figures>.
8. Shen W., Liu, Y., China’s normative systems for responsible AI – from soft to hard law, published in *The Cambridge Handbook of responsible artificial intelligence*, URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/EF02D78934D18B9A22A57A46FF8FFAF/C/9781009207867AR.pdf/The_Cambridge_Handbook_of_Responsible_Artificial_Intelligence.pdf?event-type=FTLA.
9. Stoica, A; Ghenade, A.; Pica, A., The impact of artificial intelligence on cyber security, published in *FAIMA Business & Management Journal*, vol. 12, București, 2024, URL: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/3110470109/fulltext/C5CF9145AB714A98PQ/57?accountid=88069&source-type=Scholarly%20Journals>.
10. Tenn, K.; Chang, Y.; Chen, H.; Fan, T.; Lin, T, Toward trustworthy artificial intelligence: an integrated framework approach mitigating threats, published in *IEEE* vol. 57, 2024, URL: <https://0k1136irj-yhttps-ieeeexplore-ieee-org.z.e-nformation.ro/document/10660603>.
11. Vincent J., „Putin says the Nation that Leads in AI ‘will be the Ruler of the World,, in *The Verge*, 2017, URL: <https://www.theverge.com/2017/9/4/16251226/russia-ai-putin-rule-the-world> apud E. Rosenbach, K. Mansted, *The geopolitics of information*, published in *Harvard Kennedy School – Belfer Center for Science and International Affairs*, 2019.
12. Zaman, S.; Alhazmi, K.; Aseeri, M.; Ahmed, M.; Khan, R; Kaiser, S., Security threats and artificial intelligence based countermeasures for internet of things networks: a comprehensive survey, published in *IEEE Access* vol. 9, 2021, URL: <https://0k1136irj-yhttps-ieeeexplore-ieee-org.z.e-nformation.ro/document/9456954>.